

ISO15016:2025 Improved Standard for Speed/Power Trials Creating a level playing field for EEDI, Newbuilding Contracts and EEXI

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Abstract Speed/power characteristics of ships determine their operational performance, fuel economy and exhaust gas production. Prior to her delivery each new ship is subjected to speed/power trials to verify that she meets the contractual agreements between owner and yard and (if applicable) that she is compliant with IMO MEPC EEDI regulations. Shaft power and vessel speed over ground are derived from on board measurements. As trials are often conducted in non-ideal conditions, the measurement of the actual environmental conditions and the availability of reliable correction methods for shallow water, wind, waves and current are essential to achieve the required accuracy. In 2015 IMO MEPC adopted ISO15016:2015 as the standard for the assessment of speed and power for the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI).

Over the last decade important developments in on-board measurements and correction methods have been achieved by the Sea Trial Analysis Group (STA) and by the specialist committees of the International Towing Tanks Conference (ITTC). The recent revision of the ISO standard is based on the foundations of the work of STA and ITTC. The application of correction methods for wind, waves and shallow water have been made consistent while ambiguities are avoided. Measurements of wind and waves have been specified and new limits for allowable weather conditions in relation to ship size have been agreed. The resulting ISO15016:2025 was published in February 2025 and replaces and cancels all previous ISO15016 editions. The modernized and improved standard offers a practical and more reliable standard for speed/power trials and enables a level playing field for EEDI and new building contract trials as well as for EEXI-trials on existing ships. In April 2025 IMO MEPC83 adopted ISO15016:2025 for EEDI. In this paper the main revisions are presented.

Keywords: *Speed/Power Trials, ISO, Standard, Direct Power Method, Wind Correction, Wave Correction, Shallow Water Correction, Ballast-Design Draught Conversion, Wind Speed Limit, Wave Height Limit.*

1 Introduction

Speed/power trials are conducted to establish the performance of the vessel at design draught and trim under stipulated weather conditions, usually deep water, no wind and no waves. As the conditions encountered during the trials often deviate from the contract conditions, corrections are applied during the analysis and reporting of the trial measurements. In the past institutes such as BSRA, NSMB, SNAME and ITTC published methods for conducting and analysing speed/power trials. Shipyards arbitrarily selected and developed their own “yard standard”. In 2002, the International Standard Organisation (ISO) published the first edition of ISO15016, an analysis method based on the propeller open water diagram and added resistance calculated by a wide choice of different correction methods and empirical data. The application of this first edition led to adverse trial experiences and to the acceptance of delivery of ships unable to meet the required schedule and burning significantly more fuel than promised with the contract and the sea trial results.

This was the reason why Shell, Nedlloyd and MARIN initiated the Sea Trial Analysis Joint Industry Project (STA-JIP). The objective was to develop transparent, practical and reliable best practices for conducting and analysing speed/power trials utilising present day knowledge and methods for modern ships. The speed/power trial analysis and reporting had to be completed on board within one hour after completing the speed runs. Leading shipowners from Germany, Greece, Japan, Denmark, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden joined the STA-JIP and contributed trial results of 30 recently delivered vessels. A gap-analysis showed the need to improve the basic trial procedures and method of analysis, as well as the correction methods for wind, waves and shallow water. The selected analysis approach was the Direct Power Method where all corrections are directly expressed in power

deviations. Conducting extensive tank testing, wind tunnel measurements and CFD analysis, dedicated correction methods for wind and waves were developed and validated.

Once the STA-JIP found its bearing and showed results from the case studies, more owners and all major yards from Korea joined this Joint Industry Project. Besides the introduction of the Direct Power Method and new correction methods for wind and waves, research efforts also focused on the conversion of trial results at ballast draught to the (contract) design draught as this proved to be one of the sources of unreliability of trial results.

The STA Recommended Practice, and the Recommended Analysis were delivered as an international industry standard in 2006. As several items such as the shallow water correction required further development and validation work, STA-Group continued the work with the support of 37 members including owners, yards, operators, class societies and independent research organizations.

In 2012 IMO MEPC required a reliable standard for the determination of ship power and speed to assess EEDI. ITTC and STA worked closely together. The specialist committee of ITTC scrutinised the scientific background of the STA approach. This resulted in the first edition of the ITTC Recommended procedures and guidelines, Preparation, Conduct and Analysis of Speed/Power Trials. This edition and later the ITTC2014 were adopted by MEPC for EEDI.

In the meantime, ISO TC8/SC6 started the revision of ISO15016:2002 for EEDI use. Both ITTC and STA-Group participated in the ISO Working Group and contributed with available methods, data and validation results. The Direct Power Method and most of the correction methods from STA/ITTC were endorsed. To improve the accuracy of the results, a lot of attention was given to the practical execution of the measurements and the methodology of application of the theoretical methods. To eliminate the effect of tidal, ocean and coastal currents, the 'Iterative Method' was introduced next to the proven 'Mean of Means' method. In 2015 MEPC adopted ISO15016:2015 for EEDI. The software implementation of this standard named STAIMO was provided by STA-Group as freeware available from www.staimo.com and is in use by yards, owners, trial engineers and verifiers worldwide. This software package enables the parties to create analysis and reporting results on board within one hour after completion of the speed runs.

Since 2015 both ITTC specialist committees and STA-Group continued their efforts to improve reliability and precision of the ISO-standard. ITTC conducted research into the G-modulus of propeller shafts, wind measurement systems and -correction methods. The SNNM-method for the correction of the effect of waves was validated by ITTC. STA efforts resulted in wind- and wave measurements, wind drag coefficients from CFD calculations and wind tunnels and comprehensive R&D into the shallow water effects on power leading to the Raven correction method.

Figure 1 Ship borne sensors for wind and wave measurement (Courtesy: MARIN)

In November 2020, ISO TC8/SC6 decided to revise ISO15016:2015. From the start it was clear that the standard had to be harmonized with the recent trial procedures of ITTC. At the same time the achievements and the trial experience of the STA-Group could not be ignored. Measurement technologies from adjacent sectors such as the offshore oil, gas, and the wind turbine industry were reviewed and included where needed and where possible. To achieve the specified target accuracy of 0.1 knot in ship speed and 2 per cent in ship power, the application of correction methods has been made consistent, and ambiguities were avoided by improving the description of the practical execution and the application of methods. The standard was also revised to accommodate EEXI-trials on existing vessels without specific model test results. The four-year revision was conducted by TC8/SC6/WG17 comprising of more than 40 international experts originating from all relevant stakeholders.

The resulting comprehensive Draft International Standard (DIS) was approved in the ISO ballot procedure with votes from 21 national member organizations. ISO15016:2025 (reference [1]) has been published in February 2025 and is available from www.iso.org. The 2002 and 2015 editions are thus withdrawn and should not be used anymore.

In April 2025 the standard was adopted by IMO MEPC83 for EEDI.

2 Speed and Power

EEDI and most newbuilding contracts are based on ship speed and power in ideal environmental conditions, i.e. deep water without current, wind or waves. In reality speed/power trials are mostly conducted in areas with current, wind and waves and sometimes restricted water depth. The effect of current is eliminated by conducting sufficient double runs on reciprocal courses. To determine the speed-power curve such double runs must be executed at a minimum of three power settings when the curve from model test is available and otherwise at a minimum of four power settings. The speed over ground for each run is found from the head way distance, the length travelled in the heading direction which is derived from the recorded GPS vessel positions at the start and end of each run and the compass course. By applying either, the Mean of Means Method or the Iterative Method the speed through water is derived. The absorbed propulsion power is derived from the torque and rpm measured on the propulsor shaft. To correct the effects of wind, waves and shallow water, computational models are used to calculate the increase in resistance and the additional power required. In adverse weather such corrections can mount up to 30 percent of the power in calm water. The validity and accuracy of the correction method thus has a substantial effect on the accuracy of the trial results. For that reason, speed-power tests must be conducted in good to moderate weather conditions. Although continuous efforts have been made to develop and improve practical computational models for added resistance in waves and wind, these models are certainly not perfect.

The computation of added resistance in waves is most reliable in head waves. For ship roll, steering and drift no corrections are applied because the available theoretical methods for full scale power influence are not accurate enough. For these reasons the double runs are conducted into and following the dominant wave direction (or wind direction when wind is dominant).

3 Wind

It is evident that the accuracy of correction methods for wind and waves require equally accurate input of the actual wind and wave conditions encountered. This information can only be obtained by adequate sensor systems (Figure 1). Even with measured data as input, in adverse weather the correction methods can lead to substantial errors in the overall trial results. Therefore, strict limits to the acceptable weather conditions for speed power trials are required.

ISO15016:2025 specifies to measure the wind by remote sensors such as Lidar, ahead of the vessel to avoid disturbance by hull and superstructures. Alternatively, 3-D ultrasonic wind meters may be used. In milder wind conditions it is still allowed to use traditional anemometers such as the cup-, propeller- or 2-D ultrasonic-type. The maximum allowable wind speed (10 minutes average at 10 m height) in relation to the type of wind sensor is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Limits for permissible wind velocity

For the wind correction, the true wind speed during the trials is derived from vector averaging of the wind measured in the two opposing runs of each double run. The vector averaging process is specified in the standard.

The averaged wind speed is corrected to a reference height of 10 m. (This is the same reference height as used in wind tunnels) The resulted wind speed and direction are then used as input for the computation of the added wind resistance of the vessel for each run. For this purpose, use is made of wind drag coefficients derived from (in given priority):

- a. Wind tunnel tests for the specific ship geometry,
- b. Computational Fluid Dynamic flow calculations for the specific ship geometry,
- c. The ship type data sets provided by the standard,
- d. Fujiwara regression formula specified in the standard.

The revision has included extensive sets of wind drag coefficients for present day ships in specific loading conditions. Those wind drag coefficients have been derived from CFD-studies and wind tunnel tests.

4 Waves

Over the last two decades more sophisticated computational models for added resistance in waves have been developed. However, validation of those models has been done with tank tests and not with full scale vessels. Four issues had to be resolved in the ISO revision process: firstly, a selection of reliable wave correction methods; secondly a priority ranking in these methods based on the weather conditions during the trial and the available data; thirdly a consistent scheme when to apply which method (in the 2015 edition, as well as in ITTC procedures, a range of methods was offered without clear ranking and application rules which lead to cherry picking). Finally, it had to be assured that accurate wave data will be used as input for these calculation models.

Following ITTC recommendations, the use of transfer functions of added resistance from seakeeping model tests has been selected as the most accurate correction method for waves. If no seakeeping test data are available, the SNNM method as validated by ITTC, shall be used to compute the transfer functions. It was clear that in both cases comprehensive and accurate spectral wave data is required as input to ensure the claimed accuracy. For this reason, the new standard specifies the measurement of the wave spectrum in the speed/power trial area. Nowadays a variety of valid and affordable wave measurement devices are available commercially-off-the-shelf.

Figure 3. Wave buoy and ship borne wave radar

Use can be made of permanently moored wave buoys, free drifting deployable compact buoys (Fig. 3), ship borne wave radars (Fig. 3) or drones. Provided that the trials are conducted at daylight with good visibility, in mild sea states and if no measured wave data are available, wave height and direction may be derived from visual observation by multiple experienced mariners for using the STAWAVE-1 method. This dedicated and practical method is validated by ITTC and only requires wave height, length of the bow section and ship beam as input. In the ultimate case that waves cannot be measured and STAWAVE-1 cannot be used due to significant heave and pitch, SNNM may be used with a PM-spectrum using the observed wave height and period as input.

The allowable significant wave height during the speed/power trials is related to the length of the vessel and wave measurement/observation as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Limits for permissible wave height

5 Shallow Water

An important improvement of ISO15016 is the introduction of the Raven-method for the correction of shallow water effects. Deep water is the preferred condition for speed/power trials, nevertheless trials sometimes must be conducted in water depths that affect the speed/power performance. For this purpose, in the past the method published by Lackenby in 1965 was used for correction of shallow water effects. However, STA identified serious shortcomings in Lackenby's approach and data. Comparisons of trial results of the same vessel in deep and restricted water depth demonstrated that this method, which was published more than sixty years ago, is far from accurate. With support of STA and the Dutch Government, MARIN conducted therefore the Shoal Power research project, leading to a new practical correction method developed by Raven.

Figure 5. Comparison of Raven and Lackenby methods with trial results of research vessel under full power for various waterdepth/draught ratios

Raven (reference [2]) separately considered shallow-water effects on the quantities determining the engine power at a given speed. From computational studies and available experimental data, he derived corrections for the principal effects, on viscous resistance and sinkage. Dedicated speed/power trials with three vessels were conducted in calm weather conditions, in three to four water depths including the deep-water case. The results were compared to the computational results from Lackenby and Raven. It was found that Raven predicts the effect of shallow water on speed/power systematically better (Figure 5). In 2017 the specialist committee of ITTC reviewed and approved the method. In ISO15016:2025 the Raven method is specified for correcting the effects of shallow water.

6 Conversion from Trial Draught to Design Draught

As several ship types such as containerships and dry cargo vessels, due to lack of cargo, cannot be subjected to speed/power trials at their design draught condition prior to delivery, results of the trials at ballast draught must be converted to the contractual design draught and trim conditions. This conversion is based on the difference between calm water model test results for the trial condition and those for the design condition. This has proven to be one of the main causes of unacceptable deviations and discrepancies in the results of speed trials.

Figure 6. STA-JIP subjected 14000 TEU MSC SAVONA to speed/power trials in both ballast draught and design draught (Courtesy: Claus Peter Offen)

Model test results are always extrapolated to full scale based on scaling laws, as well as “correlation coefficients”. These statistical correlation coefficients relate the scaled-up model test power to the predicted power for the actual speed/power trials with that vessel. For a model basin with a reliable trial database for the specific ship type and size, this practice is proven to be able to deliver power predictions with acceptable accuracy.

Model test prediction accuracy is thus dependent on the experience of the model basin and their active collection of accurate speed/power trial data. However, as explained above, for several ship types, trial results at design draught are scarce. This is a particular problem for relatively new ship types and sizes.

STA-Group conducted dedicated speed/power trials amongst others on three container vessels, in the range of 6000 to 14000 TEU at design draught and trim and compared the results with the results of the original delivery trials at ballast draught. This comparison for MSC SAVONA (Figure 6) is presented in Figure 7 (reference [3]). The results of the trials at design draught with a clean hull in deep water and in benign weather resulted in a 0.71 knot lower speed compared with the results of the original delivery trials. For this vessel this speed discrepancy corresponded to a power deviation of 15%.

A major part of this deviation could be traced back to the use of arbitrary extrapolation coefficients for design draught by the particular model basin. For this reason, the ISO standard specifies that for the extrapolation of model test results used for ballast/design draught conversion of speed/power trial results, for both draughts use shall be made of the same extrapolation procedure, method and correlation coefficients. This has been further clarified in the 2025 standard.

Figure 7. Results of speed/power trials in both ballast draught and design draught on MSC SAVONA

7 Accuracy

ISO15016 is aiming at the assessment of ship speed within 0.1 knot and shaft power within 2%. When speed/power trials are conducted in ideal conditions this is certainly achievable. In practice the trials are most of the time conducted in non-ideal conditions and in those cases the accuracy of correction methods have a direct effect on the trial outcome. Although laboratories such as towing tanks, seakeeping basins and wind tunnels were

instrumental for the development of these correction methods and uncertainty studies, the overall assessment of the accuracy of speed/power trials should be based on results of dedicated systematic full-scale trials.

The STA-Group contributed such trials with 3 types of vessels each trialed in 4 different water depths to assess the accuracy of the shallow water correction (see Section 5). STA also conducted dedicated trials with container ships to quantify the effect of the ballast/design draught conversion (see Section 6).

For the wind correction and the wave correction unfortunately, such systematic full-scale validation is still missing. Correction methods for waves have been developed and validated by means of scale model tests and checked against the results of other correction models. ITTC has correlated the wave correction model SNNM to results of basic model tests for some ship types in regular waves. Accurate measurement of added resistance in short waves, which are typical for trials, requires a dedicated test set up with large ship models in an adequate large seakeeping basin equipped with advanced wave generators. Therefore, the correlations as presented only provide an indication of the bias that can be expected; they do not take into account the actual situation during trials.

As the wind resistance is proportional to the relative wind speed squared and the added resistance in waves is proportional to the wave height squared and sensitive for the wave period, the wind and wave conditions used as input for the correction methods have a dominant effect on the accuracy of these corrections. Reliable measurement of the wind and wave conditions during the trials is thus crucial for accurate corrections. Shipyards (and owners) should use the best available sensors and deny the use of outdated equipment.

An overall assessment of the accuracy of the speed/power trial conduct and analysis is still missing. For this purpose, it is recommended to conduct dedicated trials with the same vessel with the same loading condition in various weather conditions including the ideal condition. For each weather condition the measured speed and power should then be corrected towards ideal conditions and to those results shall be compared. Obviously, this process should be conducted for different ship types and sizes.

In this way the error in the final results can then be quantified and related to the weather condition. Based on these results and the target accuracy, the limits for allowable wind speed and wave height can then be further improved.

There is certainly room for improvement in the sea trial analysis but it means that more work has to be done at sea in the real world.

8 Conclusions

Over the last four years ISO15016 has been revised and modernized in a close co-operation between ISO, STA-Group and ITTC. Taking into account the R&D efforts of STA and the validation work conducted by ITTC over the last decade, significant improvements have been achieved in corrections of the effects of wind, waves and shallow water. The selection and application of the correction methods has been defined to avoid ambiguities. Accurate measurements of wind and waves with modern sensor systems have been specified whereas for benign weather conditions traditional methods are still allowed. The limits for allowable wind and waves are stricter and take into account the method of measurement to reduce the overall uncertainty. The Raven-method is specified for more reliable power correction to shallow water effects. Strict and clear rules on the conversion of trial results at ballast draught to design draught are in place.

ISO15016:2025 was published in February 2025. In April 2025 the standard has been adopted by IMO MEPC83 for EEDI speed/power trials. The outdated editions from 2002 and 2015 are withdrawn and should not be used anymore.

STA Group has implemented the ISO15016:2025 in the STAIMO 3.0 software which is made available as freeware from www.staimo.org.

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